

The Qumran 4Q1 and 4Q9 Fragments without Photograph in DJD XII

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On the plates of the editions of 4Q1 and 4Q9 in DJD XII,¹ four fragment numbers were included without a photograph but with the text “no photograph,” namely on Plate V 4Q1 frags. 57, 58, and 61, and on Plate XIII 4Q9 frag. 13. On p. 30 the editor, James R. Davila, comments on 4Q1 frags. 57 and 58: “There is no photograph of this fragment,” and on frag. 61 “There is another fragment of 4QGen-Exod^a that bears unreadable letter traces and has not yet been photographed.” On p. 72 he comments that “As of July, 1990 no infrared photograph was available for [4Q9] frg. 13, so that more of the text could not be read.” Apparently Davila had been able to consult these fragments in the Rockefeller Museum, where he transcribed what was legible to the naked eye. However, on the present IAA plates of 4Q1 and 4Q9 these fragments are missing.

In 1994 the editor-in-chief of the International Dead Sea Scrolls Publication Project, Emanuel Tov, took the initiative and gave the instructions for an inventory of the relationships between the present state (1994) of the Rockefeller Museum plates and the latest PAM photographs (generally 1959 or 1960) of the same Museum plates. In between 1959/60 and 1994 many fragments had been transferred, without any record, from one plate to another. For the Dead Sea Scrolls Publication Project it seemed important to have more insight in the whereabouts of many fragments.

The main work was done first by Hayeon Kim, then doctoral student of Tov, and subsequently by Jan Karnis and Eva Ben-David. Much of the inventory was recorded in two yellow notebooks. Scans of these notebooks and other materials relating to the inventory were xeroxed by Eibert Tigchelaar, who reorganized the pages according to Rockefeller plate number. An electronic version of Tigchelaar’s scans is accessible at the Orion Institute at the Hebrew University of Jerusalem.

These notebooks contain two pages relevant for these unphotographed 4Q1 and 4Q9 fragments.

(see next page)

¹*Qumran Cave 4.VII: Genesis to Numbers*, ed. Eugene Ulrich et al., DJD 12 (Oxford: Clarendon, 1994).

The first page mentions:

Add UN[N]UMBERED PLATE in drawer with RO 63
additional fragments?

J. Davila has a note on it

4QGen^{h,a}

he says they all need to be photographed

and shows drawing of these five fragments.

In these notebooks the abbreviation 'RO' (short for ROC) refers to the Rockefeller Museum Plate. Presently such (Museum) Plates are referred to as IAA (Israel Antiquities Authority) Plates. The DJD (Discoveries in the Judaean Desert) editions refers to them as Mus. Inv.

The second page mentions, more briefly:

Add ? in drawer with RO 63
No RO. NUMBER
4QGen ?

and also provides drawing of those fragments.

Add ? IN DRAWER WITH RO 63
NO RO. NUMBER 5 frags

4Q gen ?

Solved
from 43.221
(Ro 323)

4Q GEN EXA
?

(1) Both pages from the inventory show that one fragment (published in DJD 12 as 4QGen^{h2}) had later been identified (either by Jan Karnis or Eva Ben-David). One page refers to PAM 43.221 and RO 323, the other to PAM 43.352 and RO 483. The DJD edition also refers to PAM 43.352, but to Mus. Inv. 275. Indeed, the fragment appears both on PAM 43.221 (very top right of the photograph)² and on PAM 43.352 (top right of the photograph).³ This record shows that the fragment has been transferred from one Museum Plate to the other. It is not clear why Davila singled out this fragment that had already been photographed several times for new photographing.

(2) A second fragment on this plate is 4Q1 frag. 7. The photograph of this fragment published in DJD 12, Plate I, has been taken from PAM 43.157. Again, it is not clear why this fragment was transferred to the unnumbered Plate.

(3) The transcription of a third fragment on this plate matches Davila's transcription of 4Q1 frag. 58.

(4) A fourth fragment on this plate may be identified with 4Q9 frag. 13. Contrary to the editor's comment, this fragment has already been photographed, namely (as 4Q1 frag. 7) on PAM 43.157, which photograph allows one to identify the text with Gen 41:12-14.

(5) In the yellow notebooks of the inventory, no transcription is given of the fifth fragment, which might be either 4Q1 frag. 57 or frag. 61.

²See: <https://www.deadseascrolls.org.il/explore-the-archive/image/B-284669>.

³See: <https://www.deadseascrolls.org.il/explore-the-archive/image/B-284384>.

Stephen Reed's catalogue⁴ does not report on this unnumbered plate with five fragments. This, however, should not surprise us since Davila apparently singled out those fragments from other plates in June/July 1990, just towards the end of the period of Reed's working with the fragments and photographs at the Rockefeller Museum (ca. September 1989-Aug 1990).

I am not aware of the present whereabouts or inventory number of this plate with five small fragments which was still unnumbered in 1994 and stored in the same drawer as ROC 63, and was—to the best of my knowledge—not included among the plates photographed by Shai Halevi in the 2010s.

⁴Stephen A. Reed, Marilyn J. Lundberg, and Michael B. Phelps, *The Dead Sea Scrolls Catalogue: Documents, Photographs and Museum Inventory Numbers* (Atlanta: Scholars Press, 1994).